

PARTICIPATORY PROJECT DESIGN AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN GOVERNMENT-FUNDED PARISH DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS: A KABALE DISTRICT CASE STUDY

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of participatory project design on the success of government-funded projects, specifically focusing on parish development in Kabale District, Uganda. Utilizing a cross-sectional survey with 75 respondents, the study integrated both quantitative and qualitative analyses. The research employed descriptive, bivariate, and multivariate analytical methods to assess the relationship between participatory design and project success. A Pearson correlation matrix was used to examine bivariate correlations, and linear regression was applied to analyze the impact of participatory design on project success. The results indicate a significant positive effect of participatory project design on the effectiveness of parish development projects (coef = -0.780, p-value = 0.000). This suggests that a participatory approach is crucial for enhancing project success. The study concludes that participatory project design significantly influences project success in Kabale District and recommends focusing on defining project goals, identifying risks, and refining strategies to ensure the sustainability of parish development projects.

INTRODUCTION

Around the world, successful projects are those that satisfy business needs, completed and maintained on schedule, completed and maintained under budget, and provide the anticipated business value and return on investment (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022). Effective project management and governance techniques are among the many elements that contribute to project success. According to Akliyah et al. (2022), there are significant variables that frequently cause projects to fail; lack of user or stakeholder input, uncertain or ambiguous requirements or specifications, adapting to new demands or standards, inadequate executive support, inadequate planning, a lack of planning when it comes to the amount of time and/or resources allotted for design, development, quality control, and/or assurance, a lack of technological know-how, inadequate resources, unfounded expectations, undefined goals, unrealistic deadlines, unproven or new technology. According to Benoit et al. (2017), the parish development model is facing numerous difficulties in its second phase, which Akliyah et

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al. (2022) have already mentioned. The reason behind this is that stakeholders were not consulted during the parish development model project design in order to help define project goals, determine results, identify risks and limits, and fine-tune project strategy before it was launched. A nightmare could come from this project's success. PDM seeks to transition 39% of families (or around 3.5 million people) from the subsistence economy to the money economy. This would eventually help to realize the third National Development Plan (NDP III), which prioritizes inclusive growth, employment, and sustainable wealth creation at the household level and is part of The Uganda Vision 2040, which envisions "a transformed Ugandan society from a peasant to a modern and prosperous country."

The sub-county will be strengthened as the lowest planning unit, and the parish will serve as the administrative and operational center for all government services, according to the widespread consensus that the PDM will bring services closer to the people. In actuality, the entire model was budgeted for at Shs200 billion in FY 2021/22, of which Shs182 billion has been appropriated under local government and Shs120 billion is the revolving money for the identified parishes in the 146 districts of Uganda. In the current fiscal year, the government intends to give each parish Sh17 million, and in the following fiscal year, it will climb to Sh100 million. Following the launch, the parish revolving funds will be distributed through SACCOs with the assistance of the parish chiefs, and pre-launch activities such as the distribution of bicycles to the LC1 and LCII chairpersons and motorcycles to the LCIII chairpersons are already underway nationwide. The PDM, however, is facing a number of new problems. First, the Ministry of Local Government (MoLG) has not yet completed the enterprise groupings and implementation instructions. Second, some districts do not have functional entities like the District Service Commission to complete the hiring of parish chiefs. Despite the government giving all districts the tools, they needed to hire parish chiefs, and just 80% of them met the deadline of September 30, 2021. Some districts' hiring practices did not adhere to the MoFPED's requirements for qualifications (Kerrigan et al., 2017). This occasionally occurs in conjunction with a delay in the public service commission approving the positions. As a result, the Sh200 billion Parish Development Model funding has been suspended by the Ministry of Finance, Planning, and Economic Development. However, this is linked to the project beneficiaries' insufficient input into project design prior to the project's launch. Based on the idea that users should be involved in the designs they will be using and that all stakeholders, including and especially users, have equal input into interface design, participatory design is a democratic process for the design of systems requiring human activity (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Parish development model

According to Yusuf et al. (2019) the Parish Development Model (PDM) is founded on the idea that ordinary individuals, who are the final users of social services, are better positioned to identify and address their own needs, priorities, and direct use of resources. The goal is to further the decentralization process, raise local responsibility, increase household incomes, and enable inclusive, sustainable, balanced, and equitable socioeconomic development. According to the Model, the PARISH serves as the hub for multi-sector community planning, implementation, oversight, and accountability. Parish is used as the lowest reference level for planning, allocating funds, and implementing initiatives to promote socioeconomic change. Under the seven pillars of production, storage, processing, and marketing; infrastructure and economic services; financial inclusion; social services; mindset change; parish-based management information system; and governance and administration, it is claimed that the PDM will generate wealth, employment, and higher household incomes (Kraisame, 2018).

The PDM is a government strategy that provides a range of services and includes: The Model suggests setting up mechanisms and infrastructure to facilitate the processing and selling of agricultural goods from Uganda; creating national household data to guide government interventions, Parish-level farmers will be coordinated through

regional commodity clusters to boost output and productivity, resulting in sustainable agricultural production. Farmers will have access to financial business management training, agricultural extension services, and construct the mechanisms and infrastructure required for the processing and marketing of Uganda's agricultural goods, enhancing local community participation in planning to jointly identify and overcome structural constraints affecting regional economic development, addressing grassroots community-level vulnerability of young people, women, and people with disabilities

Coffee, cotton, cocoa, cassava, tea, vegetable oils (including palm oil), maize, rice, sugar cane, fish, dairy, beef, bananas, beans, avocado, shea nuts, cashew nuts, and macadamia nuts are among the priority commodities for the parish model. The PDM is in line with the following five strategic goals of the NDPIII: Strengthen private sector ability to spur growth and generate jobs; and Enhance value addition in Key Growth Opportunities, Improve the quantity and quality of productive infrastructure by consolidating it and Improve population productivity and wellbeing, and strengthen the state's role in directing and encouraging development.

The following principles guided the Parish Development Model: In order to mitigate the diseconomies of scale (in savings, production, marketing, and extension services), poor quality inputs/output, lack of reliable production advice, information (on), and connectivity to commodity and financial markets as well as post-harvest losses, associations are being formed to help Ugandans who are currently operating in the subsistence economy access quality inputs, tailored technical assistance, guaranteed markets, subsidized credit, etc. Market-based measures that reinforce value chains stimulate competitiveness, efficiency, and innovation which will eventually reduce the need for government support, are encouraged by the PDM.

Project success

A project that completes its goals on time and within budget has traditionally been considered successful (Benoit et al., 2017). The evaluation criterion has persisted as the most prevalent measurement in many businesses, according to Turyasingura et al. (2021). However, in order to be successful, a development project must also offer the benefits and live up to the expectations of all parties involved, including beneficiaries, stakeholders, donors, and financing organizations. However, establishing these measures of success is more challenging, and some of them can only be assessed years after the project is over. Many organizations find it challenging to conduct these kinds of evaluations due to a lack of money (Benoit et al., 2017). Project success and project management success must be distinguished in order to assist businesses in making assessments of success (Chen et al., 2017). The degree to which the project's ultimate objectives are achieved can be used to determine the efficacy of a project, with the deliverables being evaluated in terms of benefits and stakeholder satisfaction. The degree of efficiency the project attained to meet its goals is what defines project management success. Efficiency has to do with how the project uses its limited resources to accomplish its objectives and cultivate positive connections with internal and external stakeholders (Coan et al., 2020). A project can succeed in meeting the development objectives while failing to meet the budget, schedule, and scope goals. Likewise, a project can succeed in meeting the development objectives while failing to meet the budget, schedule, and scope goals.

Turyasingura et al. (2022, 2021) state that a project can only be effective if the success criteria were established with the project beneficiaries from the beginning. In contrast to the parish development model, it is crucial to define success across three levels with project beneficiaries when starting a project:

Successful project completion

This level outlines the requirements for determining whether the process of providing project deliverables was successful. The four project constraints scope, time, budget, and quality are addressed by this criterion. The criteria are restricted to the project's lifespan and both during the project's existence and after it has been formally

concluded, success can be evaluated. This gauges how effectively a project utilized its resources to produce the project's deliverables (Watts et al., 2019).

Results success

Here, the standards by which the supplied good or service is judged successful are defined (e.g. service is used by all beneficiaries in scope, students attending school, water systems operational, certified teachers, etc.). Once the product or service is launched and for a predetermined amount of time, these characteristics must be evaluated.

Development success

This entails setting the standards by which the good or service given adds value to the recipients and enhances their quality of life (economic, health, social, etc). Examples include a 50% rise in revenue and a 25% decrease in sickness.

When a project does not achieve its development goals, it fails in the worst way possible. The use and application of a consistent, repeatable, and predictable methodology that supports the planning and implementation of development projects and elevates project management to a core competency supported by a learning-friendly environment characterizes organizations that are able to meet the criteria for success (Yusuf et al., 2019). Turyasingura et al. (2022; 2021) assert that certain elements must be taken into account for the project to be effective. Intelligent individuals, thorough planning, open communication, appropriate risk management, and strong project.

Intelligent individuals

To make a project a success, you need capable people in your team. A project can derail at any point in time. For this, the project staff and all the stakeholders of the project must share their enthusiasm and commitment with the group. The team should share similar visions for the project and aim for success. If the team is lacking, project managers will have a lot of problems. The wrong kind of leadership and an uncoordinated team might lead to a project's failure. The project manager should guarantee that each team member is given the proper task and that they are all getting along with one another (Matsukawa and Tatsuki, 2018).

Thorough planning

A thorough plan gets the ball rolling from the beginning in favor of the project's success. Always be aware of the project's direction from the start, both for the team and for the stakeholders. The team can stay organized and achieve deadlines by conducting thorough planning (Krajinović, 2020). The advantages of careful planning are numerous. A realistic time frame can be established thanks to this project's first stage. Steiner and Farmer (2018) provides a precise deadline for cost estimates to be created and aids in the clear documenting of milestones and deliverables, making things much simpler as the project moves forward. Planning provides a warning system and outlines the resource requirements. If there is a lapse, the warning system will give you a crystal-clear view of what to anticipate (Kunjuraman, 2022).

Open communication

An open line of communication is crucial to the success of a project. It is crucial for the team to stay informed about every facet of the project when working to a set timeframe. Learn when to say no as well. Making commitments that one cannot keep is improper. Be truthful about what can be provided and when it can be delivered as a project manager (Rachman and Bulkis, 2020).

Appropriate risk management

Projects frequently do not proceed according to schedule. Due to hazards that surface during a project, some fail spectacularly and others fail miserably. For every \$1 billion invested on projects and programs, businesses now lose USD 109 million, according to PMI's "Pulse of the Profession: The High Cost of Low Performance." To address risks that develop during the project, create a risk log with an action plan. Make sure as the project

manager that all the stakeholders are aware of your risk log and where to find it. Even if something goes wrong, your team can deal with it quickly thanks to the established plan. This helps the customers feel safe with the progress of their project and offers the team confidence when tackling project hazards (Mortazavi, 2021).

Strong project closure

A project needs a solid closing to be successful. As the project manager, you must stand your ground and concur with the client that all essential success criteria have been satisfied. Delivery of the project, testing, and release approval must be agreed upon and approved. Organizations have discovered that hiring certified project managers is a crucial factor in project success in addition to the previously mentioned factors (Perry et al., 2017). Having credentialed project managers increases an organization's overall success in terms of the KPIs of quality, scope, budget, schedule, and business advantages, according to community projects journey "Insights and Trends: Current Portfolio, Programme, and Project Management Practices."

Participatory project design

User input is required for participatory design to be used in practical applications. The idea that users should be involved in the designs they will be using and that all stakeholders, including and especially users, have equal input into interaction design underlies the democratic process known as participatory design, which is used to create social and technological systems involving human work (Turyasingura et al., 2021). Stakeholders are included in the design process from the very beginning through participatory design. The design process might be more open to taking the project into consideration thanks to the involvement of stakeholders and end users together. Participatory design encourages a more creative development environment, which is conducive to user-centered design innovation. One technique that highlights the significance of developing cooperative innovation strategies that put people at the center of the technical development process is the following: Cocreate, brainstorm, user: job/task scenario, system developers: component, and so on. According to Agaba and Turyasingura (2022) managing a community's decision-making process over whether to take on the project or not requires doing feasibility assessments throughout project design. They can provide objective, expert third-party inquiry, including cost-benefit analysis, alternative options, and confirmation, which can eventually result in project sustainability.

According to Trisiana (2020) who agrees with the viewpoints of the aforementioned academics, project feasibility findings are essential for the sustainability of both government- and donor-funded initiatives if the community was involved in their creation. By including the community in project design, Sulistyawati et al. (2019), affirms that feasibility findings support whether a project is viable or not. The information provided above, however, does not demonstrate how projects are feasible or how the results of the feasibility studies are shared with the community. Training of stakeholders encourages the sustainability of projects; once project supporters are participating in project training, they will take up the project from the beginning till donor exit, resulting in project sustainability (Saragi et al., 2020). The project becomes more efficient, effective, and relevant to the recipients as a result of including stakeholders in mutual inspection and monitoring. It considers the significance of enabling community members to take part in project activities, hence ensuring project sustainability. The longevity of donor-funded initiatives depends on developing local people's skills for taking their opinions into consideration and giving them more opportunity in planning and directing the review process.

According to Siswanto and Utomo (2020) indigenous people, community groups, and other stakeholders jointly choose how to monitor outcomes and what steps should be taken after this data has been gathered and reviewed.

Singh (2018) says that community involvement in project management education is a key tool in developing self-governing and authorized communities, inspiring community members to take action and make decisions as a group.

Define project goals

The intended result of a project is referred to as a project aim by Turyasingura et al. (2021). They provide you with a broad perspective for what the project will achieve and are high-level assertions. This suggests that stakeholders should participate in project planning so that the members own the desired outcome after the project is complete. Project objectives define the HOW if project goals define the WHAT. You must complete these little tasks or actions in order to complete your project's objective. These are your deliverables, in brief (Srirejeki, 2018). Wani et al. (2022) stated that planning, implementation, execution, and evaluation processes for a project can be guided by project management objectives. These goals raise a project's chance of success, which benefits the organization, management, and staff. Knowing the value of goals can aid management in selecting which ones to set for upcoming initiatives, as well as the project beneficiaries. Therefore, in order to increase project success, stakeholders or project beneficiaries should be involved in the project design, which is not the case with the majority of government projects. Wali et al. (2017) hopes that project beneficiaries' participation in goal-setting might aid organizations in forming routines or achieving goals that last long after a project is finished. However, government initiatives are typically top-bottom, which has generally had an impact on project sustainability.

Incorporating project beneficiaries increases the success of projects LAL (2019). Setting up project management goals can help an organization complete a project with more success. Teams could decide to focus on improving their ability to collaborate and communicate. Individual team members might succeed in achieving personal objectives like improving their organization or learning a new skill (Mortazavi, 2021). The broader objectives of an organization, such as increasing the client base or diversifying the company's operations, are also supported by project management objectives. By achieving these objectives, the project team will have greater career options and will be seen as a valuable asset by management hence project success. However, involving project beneficiaries in the ownership of their project is a nightmare with government projects. Project goals are created without consulting the intended recipients, which ultimately has an impact on how well the project will perform. Project sustainability won't exist if project success isn't accomplished. But if the project's goal was established alongside its intended beneficiaries, the initiative would be successful, leading to project sustainability. Defining the project's objective in a collaborative manner creates a focus on goals, resulting in project success. According to Turyasingura and Agaba (2022), sharing goals with project beneficiaries might enhance a project team's attention to tasks. In order for teams to work toward the desired goals, it is crucial to specify expected results. As they work toward a specific objective, this technique can also assist professionals in maintaining more effective practices. Because professionals are more likely to feel a sense of success when they achieve their goals, it could also improve morale. Involving stakeholders in the process of developing project goals is essential for every type of project since it improves operational procedures (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022).

Professionals can review routine operational procedures and find ways to make them more efficient since project management goals set up clear expectations. Professionals can accomplish these goals more quickly and improve the company's future operations by modifying these processes to match the project's objectives. It is uncommon in government projects, though. Government professionals create projects and employ individuals. The success of government projects has been impacted by this.

Determine results

Line workers and beneficiaries in particular get the possibility to be full partners in deciding the direction and efficacy of a project when project results are determined in a participatory manner. It can provide individuals who

are frequently unheard a voice (Dudgeon et al., 2017). This will support the project's success and once more, it will assist the project beneficiaries in taking ownership of their work and actively taking part in decision-making. The fact that this is just a government effort and government projects are unsustainable for this reason. Project success and sustainability are impacted when project end users are not involved in defining project results. Experienced community builders understand how crucial it is to involve stakeholders the people who are directly involved with and impacted by their projects in their work (Fifield, 2020). It provides them with the knowledge they require to plan their activities and to modify them as necessary to best meet the requirements of the neighborhood and of the specific people that an intervention or program is intended to assist. This is especially true when it comes to defining project results in a participatory manner.

The majority of people picture something that occurs at the conclusion of a project that evaluates the project after it is over and determines whether it was successful or not when they think of defining project results (Turyasingura et al., 2021). Any project should truly start by identifying its goals and objectives from the outset. In participatory project definition, all project participants those who will be directly impacted by or responsible for carrying out the project are invited to contribute to its understanding and use of that understanding to better the work. Participatory project results definition involves more than just inviting stakeholders to participate. Participating everyone involved transforms a project from something done for a group of people to something done with them. Without respect and mutual trust, planning and assessment cannot be done. These must be developed through time, but whether you are working in a developing country or in an American metropolitan area, the development is more likely if you start off with an understanding of the local culture and customs. Long-term trust and commitment will be greatly facilitated by respecting people and the information and abilities they possess.

Identify project risks and constraints

A risk is an event that may or could not occur and cause undesirable outcomes or losses. A constraint is a practical restriction on what is possible for the project. Both must be properly managed. According to Gohori and Merwe (2022), at the start of projects, the risk exposure is highest. In order for members to own the decisions made about them, it should be identified with project beneficiaries during project design. The lack of knowledge at the start of programs when beneficiaries have not taken part causes a high level of uncertainty. Project managers with common sense start spotting dangers early on. Additionally, include a list of your greatest risks in the project charter and although it does happen occasionally in government-funded enterprises. The beneficiaries of the project are not a part of the system that failed them. Every fiscal year, the government introduces new initiatives and programs. Evaluations are completed at the end of the year but are not shared with stakeholders so that they might identify project risks and constraints that are likely to occur in the future. This suggests that all initiatives will continue to fail and cost tax payer's money. There are many methods for identifying project dangers before they happen (Febriani and Utomo, 2019). It's possible that project managers will desire to combine these strategies. For instance, during one of their weekly meetings, the project team might go through a checklist, and then in a later meeting, they might go over assumptions and choose important players.

Schedule the interviews and specify your inquiries. Keep a record of the interview's outcomes and a project's goals. What are [project objective, where project objective may be scheduling, money, quality, or scope biggest]'s risks.

Project managers can make errors in project risk identification that have an impact on the success and sustainability of the project (Filippi and Cocina, 2022). The failing to identify dangers early on when doing so would be cheaper, failing to repeatedly detect hazards, risks are not recognized with the proper project beneficiaries, they are not identified utilizing a variety of risk identification methodologies, they are not collected

in one place, and they are not made visible and simple to access and risks are not recorded in a standardized manner.

Refine project strategy

The "triple constraint" delivering the project on time, within budget, and in accordance with specifications is the foundation of conventional measurements of project success. Short-term thinking is the foundation of doing this. Projects are approached with the mantra from Nike, "Just Do It!" - Here are the requirements, the timeline, and the budget. Schedule and money are the primary project success indicators in this reactive attitude. Specification is typically the item we give up if we have to (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022). The feature or capability that customers expected is not provided. Why should they not be unhappy with the project's outcomes? Different metrics for project success and alternative project management practices are required and strategic project management is required. They need to be more than merely operational or tactical. The immense potential that projects bring must be seized by corporations. In order to guide project actions and decision-making as the project environment changes, project strategy offers a broad framework or canopy.

The active involvement of projects in the strategic intent of the organization should be encouraged. A strategic plan which serves as the corporate level equivalent of a company's strategy. The marketing strategy serves as corporate strategy. The business plan contains the foundation for the marketing plan derived from the operational plan.

Plans are the result of every strategy. But the project schedule is what it is. No project strategy exists (Haldane et al., 2019). The project lacks a strategy. Every strategy and plan must incorporate and expand upon the ones that came before. The project plan does not include any other strategies or plans into it or build upon them. Instead, it concentrates on methods for carrying out activities and finishing deliverables. But for what objective? That is a short-term perspective: to finish the project on schedule, on budget, and in accordance with specifications. The initiative should, in the long run, give the company a competitive advantage or add value. For projects to be more valuable and yield better results, a project strategy is crucial (Turyasingura and Agaba, 2022). "The project viewpoint, direction, and guidelines on what to do and how to do it in order to obtain the maximum competitive advantage and the best value from the project," is how we define project strategy. Project strategy is a broad collection of rules that will be followed by the project in order to decide what to do and how to do it. The corporate, business, marketing, and operational strategies are all in line with it.

There are two types of projects: those targeted at internal consumers and those started with the goal of producing goods or services for clients outside the organization. The projects for external clients are designed to give the company a competitive edge. They supply the income, money flow, and profits. The internal customer projects are designed to add value to the company's operations. They offer cost savings, increased productivity, and quicker reaction times. They support competitive advantage in a roundabout way (Turyasingura et al., 2021). Regardless of whether a project is targeted at internal or external clients, a project strategy is necessary. The project strategy aids in keeping the project focused on the desired strategic results, enabling it to achieve its goals by asking and answering the Why, What, How, Who, When, and Where questions at a high level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research design

This study's cross-sectional survey research approach included quantitative and qualitative methods. While a quantitative technique aids in describing the present situation and looking into cause-and-effect correlations between the research variables, a qualitative approach aids in understanding and exploring the depth, richness, and complexity inherent in the phenomenon being studied (Haynes et al., 2019). Using the qualitative method, the researcher was able to gather comprehensive justifications for how participatory project design contributed to

the success of a government-funded project in Uganda, specifically a case study of the Parish Development Model in the Kabale District.

Area of study

The study was restricted to the local government of the Kabale District. The Republic of Uganda's Kabale District is located in the southwest. Its coordinates are 00° and 00° South latitude and 29° 45' to 30° 15' East longitude. It shares borders with the Republic of Rwanda to the south, Rukiga to the east, and the districts of Rubanda to the west. The Kabale district has a total area of around 575 square kilometers (222 m²). Between Kampala and Kabale, there are 337 km (209 miles) (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022).

Study population

Local administrative units that make up the Kabale District local government include Maziba, Kaharo, Kyanamira, Buhara, Katuna town council, Ryakarimira town council, Rubaya, Kitumba, Kahungye, Kibuga, Butanda, Kamuganguzi, and Kabale municipality, which are divided into three regions: the southern, central, and northern. These were politicians, farmers, NGOs and business community (Agaba and Turyasingura, 2022). By ensuring participatory project design on project success with reference to Parish Development Model, each of these departments except health department is in charge of service delivery. Table 1 shows the categories of respondents.

A total of seventy-five people were selected for the study and the researcher used Yamane (1967) formula to determine the sample size as illustrated.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Therefore, 75 respondents were sampled.

Purposive techniques

Purposive sampling, according to Naiga et al. (2015), entails nonrandom selection of the sample based on the researcher's judgment and understanding of the population. The researcher chose this approach because it allows participants to be chosen based on their financial responsibility for the local government of Kabale District's service delivery. This sampling strategy was also taken into consideration by the researcher since it is cost-effective because just a small portion of the population with relevant knowledge was sampled. The researcher choose the community based services, production and marketing, commercial office, planning department and administrator approach that is appropriate for the study because it allowed for the collection of precise data and information from respondents who were deemed to be more informed and adept at the subject.

Data collection methods and techniques

The researcher used a structured questionnaire to collect information from primary sources. This gave the enumerators the chance to address any queries or concerns that the respondents had. The questionnaire was distributed to the administration, planning department, commercial office, production and marketing department, and community-based services. The researcher, two research assistants, and enumerators distributed the questionnaire. After receiving a full day of instruction in doing fundamental research, particularly through practice surveys, the enumerators were ready to take on the task of collecting data.

Data quality control

Validity

The extent to which a test captures the intended outcome is, referred to as validity. The research instrument considered each aspect of the phenomena being examined as it is defined in the conceptual framework in order

to assure validity (Turyasingura et al., 2022). In order to produce the reliable findings, conclusions and recommendations required by the study aims and issue, the researcher ensured the validity of the instruments for efficiency and effectiveness of the tools.

In order to determine whether the instruments are thorough, clear, easy, and relevant to the study objectives, they were prepared and debated with specialists in the field of research and potato projects. Using the CVI, whose formula is; a Content Validity Test was performed

$$CVI = \frac{\text{Number of relevant items}}{\text{Total number of items}} \times 100 = \frac{100}{110} \times 100 = 99.9$$

Summary of the reliability statistics

$$\text{Judge 1} = 70/75=0.933$$

$$\text{Judge 2} = 73/75= 0.973$$

$$\text{Judge 3} = 68/75= 0.907$$

$$\text{Judge 4} = 71/75=0.947$$

$$\text{Total } 3.76. \text{ Therefore } 7.76/4=0.94$$

These results implied that research instruments were valid to be used for the data collection on the community participation and sustainability of donor-funded potato projects in Kabale District. Edwards (2019) said that, for instruments to be accepted as valid the average content validity index (CVI) no. of items declared valid divided by the total No. of items = at least 0.7. Since the CVI value is above 90%, then the instruments were valid, (Njeru, (46). A questionnaire had a good content validity index of 0.94, indicating that the instrument was valid for gathering data.

Table 1. Categories of respondents.

<u>Respondent</u>	<u>Proportionately selected sample (n_i)</u>	<u>Sampling technique</u>	
Politicians	6	Simple sampling	random
Farmers	31	Simple sampling	random
Business Community	30	Simple sampling	random
NGOs	8	Simple sampling	random
TOTAL	75		

Source: Field data, 2022.

Table 2. Reliability statistics.

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Cronbach's alpha</u>	<u>Number of items</u>
Project goals,	0.956	16
Project results,	0.971	16
Risks and constraints,	0.872	16
Refine project strategy	0.891	20
Project success	0.932	20
Total	4.622	
Average	4.622/4=0.924	

Source: Field data 2022.

Reliability

When the same populations of people are evaluated repeatedly under the same conditions, reliability evaluations look at how consistently the measuring methods produce results (Joshi and Yenneti, 2020). Additionally, to check the reliability of the research tools, a pilot study is conducted with participants who were purposely and merely selected at random from the study region. Departments from these administrative, which include those for health, community-based services, marketing and production, administration, education, and natural resources, as well as those for finance, trade, commerce, and tourism, took part in a pilot study with questionnaires. Table 2 shows the reliability statistics.

The questionnaire's design, wording, completeness, and clarity were all required to check. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used to demonstrate the dependability of the instruments (Turyasingura, 2021)). The results, which suggest that the tools are more precise and valuable, are 0.76 on a Statistic Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) scale.

Therefore, if individual items are significantly connected to one another, it is implied that there is a high level of confidence in the dependability of the overall scale. The following standards are provided by Cronbach's alpha (5): "> 0.9 - Excellent, > 0.8 - Good, > 0.7 - Acceptable, > 0.6 - Questionable, > 0.5 - Poor, and_ 0.5 - Unacceptable."

RESULTS

Data management and analysis

Data management and processing

Descriptive, bivariate, and multivariate stages of data analysis were completed. The descriptive analysis resulted in the production of frequency distributions, tables, and other data. The Pearson rank correlation was utilized in a bivariate study to compute the relationships between the dependent variable and the independent variables as well as the relationships between categorical variables. Cross tabulations were once more used to show how the variables related to one another.

Source: Field data 2022.

Multivariate analysis

In this stage, the model had been fitted, and only the independent variables at the bivariate stage had shown a significant relationship with the dependent variable, had been added to the linear regression model. In other words, only variables that had been determined to be significant at the bivariate stage were regressed at the multivariate level. The multivariate model is shown in the equation below;

$$PS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PG + \beta_2 PR + \beta_3 PRC + +\beta_4 RPS + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Table 3. Showing descriptive statistics for participatory project design and project success.

Statement	SA		A		UD		SD		D	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
I was consulted during the design of parish development model	00	00	00	00	00	00	70	93.3	5	6.7
I participated in the PDM goal setting	00	00	00	00	00	00	67	90.6	33	9.4
I participated in setting activities of the PDM to determine results	00	00	00	00	00	00	75	100	0000	
I was involved in identification of PDM Risks and constraints	00	00	00	00	00	00	75	100	0000	
I was involved in refine PDM project strategy	00	00	00	00	00	00	75	100	0000	
<u>PDM project will be sustainable</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>00</u>	<u>75</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>0000</u>	

Strongly Agree (SA) 5, (Agree (A) (4), Undecided (UD) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and strongly Disagree (SD) 1.

$$PS = \beta_0 + \beta_1PG + \beta_2PR + \beta_3PRC + +\beta_4RPS + \varepsilon$$

Where PP = Project success; PG =Project goals; PR =Project results; PRC = Project risks and constraints RPS = Refine project strategy; ε =Error term.

$\beta_1PG + \beta_2PR + \beta_3PRC + +\beta_4RPS$ are the partial coefficients which explain how each of the independent variables (Well stipulated roles, Well-structured departments and Capacity of board members) impact on project success with a case of Parish Development Model. Project design were expected to have a positive effect on the project success with a case of Parish Development Model in Kabale District.

Ethical considerations

The researcher asked the Kabale District Local Government for authorization and stated that the study was solely for academic purposes. Before distributing the questionnaire, she also asked the respondents for their permission.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics for participatory project design and project success a case study of Parish Development Model project in Kabale District.

This part of the study presents the descriptive statistics based on the views of respondents regarding participatory project design and project success a case study of Parish Development Model project in Kabale District (Table 3). Participatory project design and project success is a case study of Parish Development Model project in Kabale District.

Six questions were given to respondents to see if the Parish development model in Kabale District is a case study of how participatory project design affects project success. When asked if they were involved in the formulation of the parish development model, 93.3% of respondents objected strongly, followed by 6.7% of those who disagreed. When respondents were asked a second time if they had participated in PDM goal planning, 90.6% strongly disagreed compared to 9.4% who disagreed. When asked if they had taken part in the PDM's setting of activities to decide results, 100% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the claim. All responders with 100% strongly disagreed when asked if they were involved in the identification of PDM risks and limits. When asked if I participated in the PDM project strategy refinement, 100% of respondents strongly disagreed with the claim.

Finally, when asked if the PDM project would be sustainable, 100% of respondents strongly disagreed with the claim. This suggests that the parish development model's creation did not involve input from the project's beneficiaries. Additionally, it demonstrates that the topbottom strategy adopted in this parish development model was typical in nature and frequently fails to produce long-lasting projects.

Table 4. Project success of parish development model in Kabale District.

Statement	SA		A		UD		SD		D	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
I have participated in the management of PDM	00	00	10	13.3	00	00	65	86.7	00	00
There has been effective communication	00	00	8	10.7	00	00	65	89.3	00	00
Project beneficiaries are satisfied	00	00	9	12	00	00	66	88	00	00
There is project ownership	00	00	13	17	00	00	62	83	00	00

Strongly Agree (SA) 5, (Agree (A) (4), Undecided (UD) 3, Disagree (SD) 2 and strongly Disagree (D) 1.
Source: Field data 2023.

Table 5. Correlations between the independent variables and the dependent variable (Project success).

	<u>Participatory project design</u>	<u>Project success</u>
	Pearson correlation	1
Participatory project design	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.780**
	N	75
	Pearson correlation	0.780**
Project success	Sig. (2-tailed)	1
	N	75

Source: Field data 2022.

Project success of parish development model in Kabale District

This part of the study presents the descriptive statistics based on the views of respondents regarding Project success of Parish Development Model in Kabale District (Table 4).

Four questions were posed to the respondents to determine whether the Kabale District may benefit from a parish development model project. When asked if they had been involved in the management of PDM, respondents gave their responses. Of them, 13.3% strongly agreed with the assertion, while 86.7% strongly disagreed. 10.7% of respondents who were asked if there had been good communication agreed with the statement, compared to 89.3% who strongly disagreed. When asked if the project's beneficiaries are satisfied, 12% of respondents said yes, compared to 88% who strongly disagreed. In the final question, respondents were asked if there was project ownership. Only 17% of respondents agreed with the statement, while 83% disagreed. This suggests that the Kabale district's parish development model project success may be a nightmare.

Bivariate analysis

Correlation analysis

The predictor variable for participatory project design is the link between project success and the parish development model. The correlation matrix below shows how the predictor variables and the dependent variable are related.

There is a relationship between participatory project design and project success. The data in the Table 5 show a strong positive association between participatory project design and project success ($r=0.780^{**}$; $p\text{-value}0.01$). These findings indicate a significant association between project successes using the parish development model as a case study in Kabale District.

Multiple regression analysis

This part of the study displays the multivariate results for participatory project design on project success using the parish development model as a case study in the Kabale District. The parish development model's project success was its dependent variable, and this model was chosen since it transformed it into a continuous variable. Table 6 shows that participatory project design is an independent variable that accounts for 68.78% of the variation in parish development model project success (adjusted R-squared = 0.645). According to this, the parish development model's project success would only increase by 64.5% if participatory project design was used. This suggests that different types of participatory project design may have an effect on the parish development model project's success in the District.

Table 6. Model summary.

a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate
1	0.780 ^a	0.688	0.645	0.32395

a. Predictors: (Constant), Participatory project design; b. Dependent Variable: Project success. Source: Field data, 2023.

Dependent Variable: Project success

Source: Field data, 2023.

Conclusion

The results and discussion lead to the conclusion that participatory project design and parish development model project success in Kabale District are strongly correlated. Furthermore, participatory project design frameworks have a significant impact on the parish development model in Kabale District.

Recommendation

In order to achieve the intended goals of the PDM, the following should be put in place:

- 1) Beneficiaries of the project should be provided with a platform to define the project goals of their businesses based on their zoning-determined environmental setup.
- 2) Beneficiaries of PDM are the main source for determining PDM results because they regularly assess their own performance.
- 3) Beneficiaries of the PDM Project should be involved at the project's highest level so that it is simple for them to identify risks and restrictions and create a plan for how to deal with these problems.
- 4) Those involved in the PDM implementation should define the project approach. Decision-making will be simpler as a result of the PDM beneficiaries' successful performance.
- 5) If the corruption is to be minimized directly on the group accounts, funds should be refunded from the ministry of finance planning and economic development under the direction of the office of the prime minister.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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